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Background: Meat, milk, and egg production is increasingly taking place in intensive animal feeding operations. Although these operations generate chemical, biological, and other hazardous agents in the surrounding environment, the health risks to people living in adjacent communities are unclear.

Objective: To conduct a systematic review to determine whether a relationship exists between human health and community exposure to operations where animals are produced for food.

Methods: A comprehensive search strategy was developed to retrieve relevant studies from Medline (Ovid), Global Health (Ovid), Embase.com, Scopus, and Web of Science databases.

Title/abstract and full-text screening by two independent reviewers will be conducted to identify relevant studies. We will include primary research studies focused on humans who live near animal feeding operations. Details regarding study design, study population, and health outcomes will be extracted. The Navigation Guide methodology will be used to conduct a risk of bias assessment. Meta-analysis for selected outcomes will be conducted if possible; other quantitative or qualitative approaches will also be utilized to summarize the outcome data.

Discussion: This systematic review will provide an updated assessment of the association between community exposure to animal feeding operations and the health of people living in adjacent communities.

Key words: animal feeding operations, community health, environmental health, epidemiology, intensive animal production, livestock, systematic review

63 **1. Introduction**

64 1.1 Rationale

65

66 Meat, dairy, and egg production has undergone a rapid transition towards a model
67 characterized by high stocking densities, large-scale operations, high throughput, specialization,
68 mechanization, and greater reliance on offsite inputs (Clay et al., 2020; Gilbert et al., 2015;
69 Wallinga et al., 2022). The intensive production of animals for food is, in many cases, the
70 dominant model in high-income countries and is expanding into a growing number of low- and
71 middle-income countries (Gilbert et al., 2015; Lam et al., 2019).

72

73 A growing body of literature has assessed associations between intensive animal production
74 and an array of adverse health effects among people living near these operations. Chemical,
75 biological, and other hazardous agents released to surrounding communities via several
76 exposure pathways have been hypothesized to be responsible for these effects (Gržinić et al.,
77 2023; Miralha et al., 2022). Examined hazards include (but are not limited to) hazardous air
78 pollutants (e.g., particulate matter, ammonia, and hydrogen sulfide) and zoonotic pathogens
79 (e.g., avian influenza viruses, hepatitis E virus, pathogenic *Escherichia coli*, *Streptococcus suis*,
80 *Campylobacter*, *Cryptosporidium parvum*, and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*) (Guo
81 et al., 2022; Poulsen et al., 2018).

82

83 Understanding the relationship between community exposure to intensive animal feeding
84 operations and health outcomes is essential for informing public health policies, land use
85 planning decisions, and community interventions. Previous systematic reviews assessing
86 potential risks associated with living near animal feeding operations have reported inconclusive
87 findings (O'Connor et al., 2010; O'Connor et al., 2017) but were documented to have significant
88 flaws in conduct (Nachman et al., 2017) and were inclusive of literature only up to 2014. A
89 recent review found that intensive animal feeding operations may have a negative impact on
90 health but focused on environmental justice variables instead of health outcomes (Son et al.,
91 2024).

92

93 There have been numerous publications on intensive animal feeding operations and their
94 association with human health in neighboring communities in the years since the last published
95 review (e.g., Kravchenko et al., 2018; Schultz et al., 2019), offering an opportunity for an
96 updated, rigorous examination of the evidence. By systematically synthesizing and critically
97 evaluating the available literature, this study aims to inform evidence-based decision-making
98 and promote the health and well-being of communities residing near operations where animals
99 are produced for food.

100

101 1.2 Objectives

102

103 Our objective is to conduct a systematic review of adverse health outcomes associated with
104 community exposure to animal feeding operations.

105

106 Our population of interest is human populations, including those in utero. Our exposure of
107 interest is community-based/indirect exposures (e.g., residential, school) to an animal feeding
108 operation(s) assessed using any relevant metric, including distance to the nearest operation,
109 farm and/or animal density, perceived odor, or levels of an indicator contaminant (e.g.,
110 endotoxins). We define animal feeding operations as any operation that produces land animals
111 for food, irrespective of size or methods of production. We aim to study all relevant health
112 outcomes, which includes a wide range of physician-diagnosed or self-reported outcomes,
113 ranging from quality-of-life measures to sub-clinical measures of disease (e.g., biomarkers).

114

115 We plan to test the following three hypotheses in our systematic review:

116 1. People with community-based exposures to animal feeding operations are more likely
117 to experience adverse respiratory health outcomes compared to people less exposed to
118 animal feeding operations.

119 2. People with community-based exposures to animal feeding operations are more likely
120 to experience adverse gastrointestinal outcomes compared to people less exposed to
121 animal feeding operations.

122 3. People with community-based exposures to animal feeding operations are more likely
123 to be colonized or infected with pathogens (e.g., *E. coli*, *Salmonella*) compared to people
124 less exposed to animal feeding operations.

125

126 We also plan to document other adverse health outcomes falling outside these three main
127 hypotheses that may be relevant to our review (e.g., quality of life, cardiovascular health
128 outcomes).

129

130 **2. Methods**

131

132 2.1 Eligibility criteria

133

134 The Population-Exposure-Comparator-Outcome-Study Design (PECOS) framework ([4.6.1. Table](#)
135 [1](#)) will be used to identify eligible studies.

136

137 2.2 Information sources

138

139 Our team includes an information specialist (LR) with extensive expertise in developing and
140 performing literature searches for systematic reviews. We designed database-specific search
141 terms and strategies for the following databases: Medline (Ovid), Global Health (Ovid),
142 Embase.com, Scopus, and Web of Science.

143

144 2.3 Search strategy

145

146 Our search strategy (4.6.2. Table 2) builds upon a previous systematic review’s search
147 (O’Connor et al., 2017), with a few major modifications. We added two additional concepts to
148 O’Connor et al.’s (2017) search, one composed of relevant human health outcomes, and one
149 composed of epidemiology study design concepts, to capture a more holistic set of outcomes
150 and a broader set of health-relevant studies. Therefore, our search comprises four main
151 concepts: animal feeding operations (search lines 1-8), community health terms (search lines
152 10-13), specific human health outcomes (search lines 16-33) and epidemiologic study design
153 (search lines 35-37). The epidemiologic study concept is adapted from searches available on the
154 InterTASC Information Specialists’ Sub-Group (ISSG) Search Filter Resource (ISSG, n.d.), which
155 provides researchers with study design-specific search filters.

156

157 Our search strategy was developed and modified through an iterative piloting process, and
158 various investigators (EC, RS, BK, KN) collaborated with our information specialist (LR) during
159 the entire search’s development. In addition, we used the final list of studies included by
160 O’Connor et al. (2017) as a list of benchmark studies to be returned by our search strategy. As
161 of May 10th, 2024, the search strategy returns 25,935 articles, prior to deduplication. A pilot
162 title/abstract screening of 200 of the returned studies resulted in 3 advancing to full text
163 screening (1.5%). Therefore, we anticipate that approximately 375 articles will undergo full text
164 screening in the final review.

165

166

167 2.4 Study records

168

169 2.4.1 Data management

170

171 All search results will be imported into EndNote to compile references and remove duplicate
172 records. DistillerSR (Ottawa, Canada) will be used for title/abstract and full-text screening. Our
173 final dataset will be published on Open Science Framework.

174

175 2.4.2 Selection process

176

177 During title/abstract screening, the titles and abstracts will be evaluated using the inclusion and
178 exclusion criteria to identify relevant studies (4.6.1 Table 1). Each title/abstract will be
179 independently screened by two of our reviewers (EC, RS, IH, BK, DL, ES, KN). Articles will be
180 eligible for this review when they describe peer-reviewed primary research in which
181 populations with exposures to animal feeding operations are compared on an individual- or
182 population-level basis to less- or not-exposed populations for any health outcome.

183
184 Studies that pass title/abstract screening will then undergo full text review, done by two
185 independent reviewers, to confirm whether the reference should be included in the final
186 review. Studies that do not adhere to the PECOS statement in either step will be excluded from
187 the final list of included studies.

188
189 At both stages of review, disputes between two reviewers will be resolved by a senior
190 investigator (RS, DL, ATL, KN). The first 10% of screened studies will be reviewed for quality
191 control by a third reviewer as well. All authors that will screen studies will take part in a
192 training/pilot screening process. The authors will all screen the same set of returned studies
193 (approx. 500 studies) and any disagreements among the screeners will be discussed over video
194 conference until a consensus is reached.

195
196 *2.4.3 Data collection process*

197
198 Data will be independently extracted from each included study by two investigators (EC, IH, BK,
199 ES) using DistillerSR. In the event of discrepancies in data extracted that cannot be resolved
200 with discussion between the two reviewers, a third reviewer will be consulted to reach
201 consensus. For studies that do not report all the data or are missing information, we will
202 attempt to contact the authors with an initial e-mail and one follow-up e-mail query with a limit
203 of two weeks before the data are categorized as “missing”. We do not anticipate any ethical
204 issues with regards to data availability.

205
206 All authors that will participate in data extraction will take part in a training process during
207 which each of the investigators will independently extract data from a pre-selected set of
208 studies. Each data item extracted by each extractor will be compared, and if disagreements
209 arise, it will be discussed by the entire group of extractors. In the event of duplicate
210 publications, or multiple reports of a primary study, we will collate all available data and use the
211 most complete dataset including the highest quality estimate of the exposure-outcome
212 relationship taken from all identified publications.

213
214 *2.5 Data items*

215
216 The data items collected for each study are listed in our supplementary materials (4.6.3).
217
218 2.6 Outcomes and prioritization
219
220 All health-relevant outcomes will be included. 4.6.4. Table 4 highlights several examples of
221 anticipated study health outcomes.
222
223 2.7 Risk of bias in individual studies
224
225 This review will use the Navigation Guide methodology (Woodruff & Sutton, 2014) to assess
226 each included study’s internal validity or risk of bias (RoB). The Navigation Guide methodology
227 draws on the approaches used by the US Environmental Protection Agency and the
228 International Agency for Research on Cancer, as well as the Grading of Recommendations,
229 Assessment, Development, and Evaluation (GRADE) approach. The Navigation Guide is
230 specifically designed to account for reliance on human observational studies instead of
231 randomized-controlled trials. Based on our pre-existing knowledge of the literature, we
232 anticipate that most of the studies included in this review will utilize observational study
233 designs. The Navigation Guide assesses human observational studies according to nine
234 domains: source population representation, blinding, exposure assessment, outcome
235 assessment, incomplete outcome data, selective outcome representation, confounding, conflict
236 of interest, and other bias (Eick et al., 2020). Each domain is assessed and rated individually,
237 without providing an overall risk of bias rating for each study.
238
239 We will utilize Health Assessment Workspace Collaborative (HAWC), a health assessment
240 management software designed by the US Environmental Protection Agency used to rate and
241 visualize RoB ratings (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2021). Each study will
242 undergo RoB assessment by two co-investigators (RS, DL, ATL, JL, KN). The HAWC visualization
243 tool will be used to display the findings of the RoB assessment.
244
245
246 2.8 Data synthesis
247
248 *2.8.1 Codebook*
249
250 We plan to use a coding process to analyze our data after extraction. We have created a sample
251 codebook (Section 4.6.4) based on our training dataset. Once all data has been extracted, we

252 will begin coding the data using an iterative process. During this process, new codes will be
253 created as necessary and previously coded data will be revisited as the codebook evolves.

254

255 *2.8.2 Quantitative synthesis (meta-analysis)*

256

257 We plan to conduct a traditional meta-analysis to generate summary estimates that could
258 provide insight into quantitative relationships between community exposure to animal
259 operations and adverse human health outcomes.

260

261 We will use a random-effects model to conduct our meta-analysis, as it allows for the inclusion
262 of studies that may differ in populations, exposure measurements, outcomes, and study
263 designs. Given the anticipated heterogeneity across these factors, a random-effects model is
264 more appropriate than a fixed-effects model, as it accounts for variability both within and
265 between studies.

266

267 The quantitative analysis will estimate pooled effect sizes for the exposure-outcome
268 relationships, incorporating weighted averages that account for the inverse variance of each
269 study's effect estimate. To assess heterogeneity, we will calculate the I^2 statistic and consider
270 subgroup analyses or meta-regression if possible to explore potential sources of variability, such
271 as differences in study populations, exposure assessment methods, or outcome definitions.

272

273 We will include all eligible studies in our meta-analysis and will not exclude studies based on
274 their compatibility with others. Instead, we will stratify analyses where necessary to ensure
275 meaningful comparisons and robust synthesis of evidence, including separating incident and
276 prevalent outcomes. This approach enables us to leverage the diversity in study designs and
277 populations while maintaining the integrity and inclusivity of the evidence base.

278

279 We will synthesize data into summary measures when individual studies are sufficiently similar,
280 allowing for meaningful comparisons and synthesis of findings. Quantitative synthesis will be
281 contingent upon whether study designs are compatible (e.g., all cross-sectional design),
282 exposures and outcome measures are comparable, outcome measures are reported on similar
283 scales or can be converted to the same scale, and the included studies are methodologically
284 sound. Potential summary statistics may include prevalence Odds Ratios (OR), regression
285 coefficients (β s, or mean differences), or prevalence ratios. When possible, we will transform
286 effect estimates to be comparable (e.g., log odds ratios to standard mean differences and vice
287 versa) (Borenstein et al., 2009).

288

289 Heterogeneity will be explored using I^2 statistic, a measure that quantifies the degree of
290 variability among effect sizes from individual studies. It represents the proportion of total
291 variation across studies that is due to heterogeneity rather than chance. The I^2 statistic is
292 interpreted as indicating low heterogeneity (0-40%), moderate heterogeneity (30-60%),
293 substantial heterogeneity (50-90%), or considerable heterogeneity (75-100%) (Deeks et al.,
294 2024). Although an assessment of the I^2 can be informative, it is also important to contextualize
295 this metric with other factors such as study quality, sample size, and methodological diversity
296 across studies when interpreting the meta-analysis results.

297
298 We will also perform sensitivity analyses by examining the effects of excluding studies with
299 heterogeneous results as well as performing subgroup analyses by excluding individual or
300 subsets of studies with characteristics that might be influential. For example, we may conduct a
301 sub-analysis on school exposure studies as compared to residential exposure studies. If enough
302 studies are available, a more formal approach to perform a subgroup analysis, clustering studies
303 by specific characteristics to determine the impact on statistical heterogeneity, will be
304 conducted.

305 306 2.8.3 Qualitative synthesis (SwiM)

307
308 For studies that are not amenable to quantitative synthesis, we will use the Synthesis without
309 Meta-analysis (SwiM) reporting guideline, which was developed for use in systematic reviews in
310 which meta-analyses of effect estimates may not be possible or appropriate for at least some
311 outcomes (Campbell et al., 2020). Although this guideline was developed for the presentation
312 of intervention studies rather than observational studies, many of the reporting items outlined
313 are still applicable to observational study presentation, including the need to explain criteria
314 used to prioritize results for summary and synthesis, explain and provide a rationale for groups
315 used in synthesis, describe methods used to assess certainty of the synthesis findings, describe
316 data presentation methods, and to report on the limitations of the synthesis (Campbell et al.,
317 2020).

318 319 2.9 Meta-bias(es):

320
321 We plan to assess publication bias if a sufficient number of studies are available. An evaluation
322 of publication bias is usually recommended when there are more than ten studies, as with
323 fewer studies these approaches may be unreliable (Dalton et al., 2016). Techniques such as
324 Egger's regression (Egger et al., 1997) or symmetry of funnel plots (Sterne & Egger, 2001) will
325 be utilized in combination with an assessment of the nature of the observed publication bias
326 (i.e., assessing the potential reasons for an asymmetric funnel plot).

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2.10 Confidence in cumulative evidence:

2.10.1 Quality of the evidence

Upon completion of risk of bias assessment and quantitative/qualitative data analysis, we will use the Navigation Guide methodology to rate the overall quality and strength of the evidence. Possible ratings for the overall quality of evidence are “high,” “moderate,” or “low.” The initial quality level of human observational data will be assumed to start at “moderate,” following the framework of past Navigation Guide case studies (Johnson et al., 2014; Lam et al., 2021; Lam et al., 2017; Lam et al., 2016).

Factors that may decrease the quality level of the overall body of evidence include:

1. Risk of Bias Across Studies: Study limitations – a substantial risk of bias across body of evidence;
2. Indirectness: Evidence was not directly comparable to the question of interest (i.e., population, exposure, comparator, and outcome).
3. Inconsistency: Widely different estimates of effect (heterogeneity or variability in results);
4. Imprecision: Studies had few participants and few events (wide confidence intervals); and
5. Publication Bias: Studies missing from body of evidence, resulting in an overestimate or underestimate of true effects from exposure.

Factors that may increase the quality level of the overall body of evidence include:

1. Large magnitude of effect: Upgraded if modeling suggested confounding alone unlikely to explain associations with large magnitude of effect.
2. Dose-response: Upgraded if consistent dose response gradient in one or multiple studies, and/or dose response across studies.
3. Residual confounding increases confidence: Upgraded if consideration of all plausible residual confounders, biases, or effect modification would underestimate the effect or suggest a spurious effect when results show no effect.

Study authors evaluating the quality of evidence will document their rationale supporting their ratings and all factors that contributed to their final decision. Study authors will independently evaluate the quality of evidence, then gather to compare their evaluations, discuss any discrepancies, and resolve any differences through discussion until consensus is reached, if

364 possible. The rationale for each decision overall will be recorded. Lack of consensus for the
365 rating on any specific factor does not preclude consensus on the overall quality of the evidence.
366

367 *2.10.2 Strength of the evidence*

368
369 Subsequent to rating the quality of the evidence, review authors will rate the strength of the
370 evidence. The overall strength of the evidence is based on a combination of four criteria: 1)
371 quality of body of evidence (i.e., the rating from the previous step); 2) direction of effect; 3)
372 confidence in effect; and 4) any other compelling attributes of the data that may influence
373 certainty. The results of rating the strength of the human evidence will then be compared to
374 the criteria specified in the Navigation Guide methodology for one of the following concluding
375 statements: 1. Sufficient; 2. Limited; 3. Inadequate; or 4. Evidence of lack of toxicity. Any
376 discrepancies between the reviewers' decisions will be resolved first through discussion. The
377 senior author (KN) will be the ultimate arbiter of any discrepancies that cannot be resolved
378 through consensus among the review authors. All decisions, discrepancies, and discussion will
379 be documented as part of this process and included in the manuscript to be submitted for peer-
380 review publication.

381

382 **3. Discussion**

383

384 Much of the relevant literature has focused on health effects associated with animal feeding
385 operations that could reasonably be characterized as intensive (e.g., Quist et al., 2022).
386 Operations classified as “large concentrated animal feeding operations” (CAFOs) in the United
387 States may house, for example, upward of 125,000 chickens or 10,000 pigs (United States
388 Environmental Protection Agency, n.d.). Outside countries with such clear designations,
389 however, the ability to classify an operation as “intensive” would require either enough
390 information to apply objective criteria (e.g., based on animal stocking densities), or subjective
391 use and interpretations of terminology (e.g., whether operations described as “industrial” or
392 “large” would meet the criteria for “intensive”). Given these challenges, we do not plan to limit
393 the scope of this review to specific scales or methods of production, as in prior reviews
394 (O'Connor et al., 2010; O'Connor et al., 2017; Son et al., 2024). At the end of the screening
395 process, if the selected manuscripts provide enough information to parse findings specific to
396 intensive animal feeding operations, we will do so in a post-hoc analysis.

397

398 We anticipate considerable variation across studies in methods used for characterization of
399 exposure to animal feeding operations; methods such as self-report, aggregation to a specified
400 geographical area or location, distance-based methods, interpolation, direct environmental
401 sampling of indicator contaminants, and others have been used in the literature (Casey et al.,

402 2015). Despite this, by categorizing studies with similar exposure methods and common health
403 outcomes, quantitative data synthesis across studies (i.e., meta-analyses) may still be possible.
404 If not, we anticipate there will still be value in qualitative synthesis of the weight of evidence in
405 determining whether a relationship exists between community exposure to animal feeding
406 operations and a particular health outcome.

407
408 Studies lacking detailed information on the operations (i.e., type and number of livestock, size
409 of the facility, etc.) may introduce non-systematic errors in exposure assessment, potentially
410 biasing an association estimate towards the null. If such a phenomenon were to occur,
411 individual studies included in our sample may be less likely to detect if a true association were
412 to exist.

413
414 Additionally, while our focus is on community exposures (i.e., indirect exposures, excluding
415 occupational studies), rural communities may include some people who also work in animal
416 feeding operations, raise backyard chickens, or otherwise experience direct exposures to
417 animals. Community-based studies that do not explicitly exclude populations with direct
418 exposure, or control for direct exposures in their analyses, introduce an important source of
419 potential bias. Our risk of bias assessment will be critical in evaluating studies subject to these
420 and other potential sources of bias.

421 422 **4. Other Information**

423 424 4.1 Dictionary

425
426 Health will be defined according to the Constitution of the World Health Organization as a state
427 of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or
428 infirmity (World Health Organization, n.d.).

429
430 Animal feeding operation will be defined as any operation that produces land animals for food,
431 irrespective of size or methods of production. Our use of the term should not be confused with
432 the regulatory designation “AFO” as defined by the US Environmental Protection Agency.

433 434 4.2 CRediT statement

435
436 Elizabeth A. Chatpar: Methodology, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing
437 Richard D. Semba: Methodology, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing,
438 Conceptualization, Supervision
439 Iman Habib: Methodology, Writing - Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing

440 Brent F. Kim: Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing
441 Elizabeth E. Sharp: Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing
442 David C. Love: Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing
443 Sara N. Lupolt: Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing
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445 Lori Rosman: Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing
446 Juleen Lam: Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing
447 Joan A. Casey: Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision
448 Keeve E. Nachman: Methodology, Writing - Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing,
449 Conceptualization, Supervision, Project Administration
450
451 4.3 Funding Support
452
453 This work was supported by the Silicon Valley Community Foundation.
454
455 4.4 Competing Interests
456
457 The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding this protocol's authorship, research,
458 and/or publication.
459
460 4.5 References
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4.6 Supplementary Information

4.6.1. Table 1. Eligibility Criteria Using the PECOS Framework

	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Population	Human populations, including those in utero	Any populations that are explicitly identified by their occupation or participation in activities involving direct exposure to livestock (e.g., occupational exposures, pastoralism, living on a farm, having animals in the home or backyard)
Exposure	Community/indirect exposure (e.g., residential, school) to an animal feeding operation estimated/assessed using any relevant metric, including distance to the nearest operation, farm and/or animal density, perceived odor, or levels of an indicator contaminant (e.g., endotoxins)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studies without an exposure to an animal feeding operation • Direct exposure to livestock animals (see Population exclusion criteria). • Indirect exposure via a relative who works on a farm
Comparator	Must have at least one comparator group with a different level of exposure to an animal feeding operation ^a , i.e., either less exposed or not exposed at all	Studies without a comparator group
Outcome	Any clinical, surrogate, or patient-centered health outcome; either incident or prevalent outcomes ^b	Studies without a clinical, surrogate, or patient-centered health outcome
Study Design	Epidemiologic studies including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Case-control • Case-cohort • Case-case • Cohort • Cross-sectional • Longitudinal • Ecological 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviews (e.g., systematic, scoping, narrative) • Meta analyses • Predictive modeling studies

	Case reports and case series ^a	
Types of Literature	Peer-reviewed literature	Non-peer reviewed literature (e.g., gray literature, trial registers, meeting posters, meeting abstracts, case reports)
Language of Publication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> English, German, French, Spanish, Portuguese, Italian, Mandarin Chinese, Polish, Dutch 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All other languages
Date of Publication	Any date	N/A

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- a. For inclusion in meta-analysis, studies must have at least one comparator group. We will include case reports/studies and case series without comparator groups for additional evidence as part of our synthesis but will not include them in meta-analysis.
- b. See Table 4 for examples.

4.6.2. Table 2. Proposed Search Strategy for Medline (Ovid)

1. Animal Husbandry/ or Housing, Animal/
2. ((animal* or bovine or cow or cows or cattle or beef or steer or pig or pigs or piglet* or pork or swine or porcine or hog or hogs or finisher* or sheep or lamb or lambs or mutton or goat or goats or poultry or chicken* or hen or hens or broiler* or turkey* or dairy or livestock or live stock or intensiv* or industrial* or confined or confinement or concentrated or large-scale) adj4 (feed* operation* or feed* facilit*)).ti,ab,kf.
3. (cafo or cafos).ti,ab,kf.
4. (feed lot* or feedlot* or feedyard* or feed yard*).ti,ab,kf.
5. ((animal* or bovine or cow or cows or cattle or beef or steer or pig or pigs or piglet* or pork or swine or porcine or hog or hogs or finisher* or sheep or lamb or lambs or mutton or goat or goats or poultry or chicken* or hen or hens or broiler* or turkey* or dairy or livestock or live stock) adj (operation* or facility or facilities or confined or confinement or density)).ti,ab,kf.
6. ((confined or confinement) adj3 (feed or feeding)).ti,ab,kf.
7. ((intensive or intensively or large-scale or industrial) adj3 (farm or farms or farming or livestock or live stock or animal operation*)).ti,ab,kf.
8. ((animal production or food animal production or livestock production or live stock production) adj (operation* or facility or facilities or industrial or intensiv* or high density)).ti,ab,kf.
9. or/1-8
10. Public Health/ or Environmental Health/ or Environmental Exposure/ or Inhalation Exposure/ or Environmental Pollutants/ or exp Air Pollutants/ or Water Pollutants/ or Environmental Illness/ or Environmental Monitoring/ or exp Population Density/

11. (public health* or environmental health* or environmental medicine or community health* or environmental reservoir*).ti,ab,kf,jn,jw.
12. ((public or community or communities or resident* or residence* or neighbor* or neighbour* or family or families or local* or population* or populace* or school* or preschool* or highschool* or nursery or nurseries or playgroup* or play group* or kindergarten* or student* or day care* or daycare* or "zip code*" or census) adj5 (health or disease* or impact* or effect* or exposure* or expose* or outcome* or symptom* or risk*)).ti,ab,kf.
13. ((public or community or communities or resident* or residence* or living or neighbor* or neighbour* or family or families or local* or population* or populace or school* or preschool* or highschool* or nursery or nurseries or playgroup* or play group* or kindergarten* or student* or day care* or daycare* or "zip code*" or census) adj5 (proximity or vicinity or location* or located or nearby or near or close or closely or area* or region* or density or densities or neighboring)).ti,ab,kf.
14. or/10-13
15. 9 and 14
16. exp Exanthema/ or exp Eczema/ or exp Dermatitis, Atopic/ or exp Eye Burns/ or exp Conjunctivitis/ or (rash or rashes or exanthema* or (skin adj2 irritat*) or eczema* or (dermatit* adj2 atopic) or (neurodermatit* adj2 atopic) or (burn* adj2 eye*) or (water* adj2 eye*) or conjunctivitis).ti,ab,kf.
17. "Signs and Symptoms, Respiratory"/ or exp Cough/ or exp Respiratory Sounds/ or exp Rhinitis/ or exp Pharyngitis/ or exp Rhinitis, Allergic, Seasonal/ or exp Respiratory Hypersensitivity/ or exp Dyspnea/ or exp Sneezing/ or (respiratory or cough* or wheez* or rhiniti* or "sore throat*" or "hay fever*" or allerg* or dyspnea* or (short* adj2 breath*) or sneez* or "nasal congest*").ti,ab,kf.
18. exp Immunity, Mucosal/ or exp Immunoglobulin A, Secretory/ or ("mucosal immune function*" or "mucosal immunity" or "secretory immunoglobulin*" or "secretory IgA" or SigA or "exocrine IgA" or "colostral IgA").ti,ab,kf.
19. exp Methicillin-Resistant Staphylococcus aureus/ or exp Clostridioides difficile/ or exp Enterococcus/ or exp Campylobacter/ or exp Campylobacter Infections/ or exp Psittacosis/ or exp Salmonella Infections/ or ("Methicillin-Resistant Staphylococcus aureus" or MRSA or "nasal carriage*" or "nasal colonization" or "Q fever*" or "Clostridioides difficile" or "Clostridium difficile" or "c. diff*" or Enterococcus or Campylobacter or "Campylobacter Infection*" or campylobacterios* or psittacos* or ornithos* or "salmonella infection*" or salmonellos*).ti,ab,kf.
20. exp Stillbirth/ or exp Birth Weight/ or exp Premature Birth/ or exp Infant, Premature/ or exp Fetal Growth Retardation/ or ("birth outcome*" or stillbirth* or "birth weight*" or birthweight* or (premat* adj2 birth*) or (preterm* adj2 birth*) or (premat* adj2 infant*) or (preterm* adj2 infant*) or (neonat* adj2 premat*) or (growth adj2 retard*) or (growth adj2 restrict*) or (small adj2 "gestational age*") or LBW or ELBW or SGA).ti,ab,kf.
21. exp Respiratory Physiological Phenomena/ or exp Respiratory Function Tests/ or ("lung function*" or "pulmonary function*" or "forced expiratory volume" or FEV or FWV1 or "forced vital capacity" or FVC or "Tiffeneau index" or "Tiffeneau-Pinelli index" or spiometr*).ti,ab,kf.
22. exp Respiratory Tract Diseases/ or exp Asthma/ or exp Pulmonary Disease, Chronic Obstructive/ or exp Pneumonia/ or exp Respiratory Tract Infections/ or (asthma* or "chronic obstructive pulmonary disease*" or "chronic obstructive lung disease*" or "chronic obstructive airway disease*" or COPD or COAD or "chronic airflow obstruction*" or "pulmonary emphysema*" or pneumonia* or (pulmonary adj2 inflamm*) or (lung* adj2 inflamm*) or influenza* or flu).ti,ab,kf.
23. exp Blood Pressure/ or exp Hypertension/ or exp Angina Pectoris/ or exp Myocardial Infarction/ or exp Heart Diseases/ or exp Stroke/ or exp Peripheral Arterial Disease/ or ("blood pressure*" or "diastolic pressure*" or "systolic pressure*" or "pulse pressure*" or hypertension* or angina or "myocardial infarct*" or "heart

attack*" or "heart disease*" or "cardiac disease*" or stroke or strokes or "cerebrovascular accident*" or CVA or "peripheral arterial disease*" or "peripheral artery disease*").ti,ab,kf.

24. exp Gastrointestinal Diseases/ or exp Inflammatory Bowel Diseases/ or exp Diarrhea/ or exp Enteritis/ or exp Gastroenteritis/ or exp Nausea/ or (gastrointestinal* or "inflammatory bowel*" or diarrhea* or diarrhoea* or enteriti* or gastroenteric* or nausea* or vomiting or emesi).ti,ab,kf.

25. exp Mental Health/ or exp Anxiety/ or exp Depression/ or exp Vertigo/ or exp Stress, Psychological/ or exp Psychological Distress/ or exp Emotions/ or exp Sleep Wake Disorders/ or exp Fatigue/ or exp Headache/ or ("mental health" or anxiety or anxieties or nervousness or anxiousness or depression or depressive or vertigo or vertigos or stress or distress or emotion* or mood or "sleep wake disorder*" or (sleep* adj2 disturb*) or (sleep* adj2 disorder*) or fatigue or headache* or "head pain*").ti,ab,kf.

26. exp Quality of Life/ or Quality-Adjusted Life Years/ or exp Activities of Daily Living/ or Health Status/ or exp Leisure Activities/ or ("quality of life" or (life adj2 quality) or "well being" or wellbeing or (activit* adj2 "daily living") or "outdoor activit*" or "leisure activit*" or QoL or HRQL or HRQoL or WHOQoL or euroqol or "euro qol" or eq5d or "eq 5d" or hql or hqol or "h qol" or hrqol or "hr qol" or hui or hui1 or hui2 or hui3 or "EQ VAS" or "EQ 15D" or "36 Item Short Form Survey" or "SF 36" or "12 item Short Form Survey" or "SF 12").ti,ab,kf.

27. exp Absenteeism/ or ((school* adj2 attend*) or absenteeism).ti,ab,kf.

28. exp Ambulatory Care/ or exp Hospitalization/ or exp Pharmaceutical Preparations/ or exp Anti-Bacterial Agents/ or ("healthcare utilization" or "health care utilization" or ambulatory or outpatient* or "clinic visit*" or "hospital admission*" or hospitalization* or "pharmaceutical preparation*" or medication* or antibiotic* or "anti-bacterial*" or antibacterial* or antiinfective* or "anti infective*").ti,ab,kf.

29. exp Death/ or exp Vital Statistics/ or exp Mortality/ or exp Morbidity/ or (death* or mortalit* or morbidit* or survival or fatal* or "life expectanc*" or "vital statistic*" or "burden of disease" or "disease burden" or "years lived with disability" or YLD or "disability adjusted life" or DALY* or "years of life lost" or YLL or "healthy years equivalent*" or hye or hyes or "healthy days measures" or qaly* or qald* or qale* or qtime* or daly* or "health adjusted life expectancy" or "life years equivalen*" or "well-being adjusted health expectancy").ti,ab,kf.

30. exp "Neoplasms"/ or (neoplas* or cancer* or tumor* or tumour* or malign* or oncolog* or carcinoma*).ti,ab,kf.

31. exp Immune System Diseases/ or exp Autoimmune Diseases/ or exp Arthritis, Rheumatoid/ or exp Psoriasis/ or exp Uveitis/ or exp Hypothyroidism/ or exp Lupus Erythematosus, Systemic/ or exp Multiple Sclerosis/ or exp Spondylitis, Ankylosing/ or ("Immune-mediated disease*" or (immune adj2 disease*) or (immune adj2 disorder*) or (immunologic* adj2 disease*) or (autoimmune adj2 disease*) or (auto-immune adj2 disease*) or (arthritis adj2 rheumatoid) or psorias* or uveitis or uveitide* or hypothyroidism* or hypothyreoidism* or hypothyreosis or hypothyroidea or hypothyroidosis or hypothyrosis or (thyroid* adj2 failure) or (thyroid* adj3 insufficien*) or (thyroid* adj3 deficien*) or "TSH deficien*" or "systemic lupus erythemato*" or "lupus erythematosus disseminatus" or "disseminated lupus" or "erythematoses visceralis" or lupovisceritis or "lupus erythematoses disseminates" or "lupus erythematosus visceralis" or "multiple sclerosis" or "disseminated sclerosis" or "sclerosis disseminated" or "chariot disease" or "insular sclerosis" or "sclerosis multiplex" or "sclerosis insular" or "sclerosis multiple" or "spondylitis ankylosing" or "ankylosing spondylitis*" or "ankylosing spondylarthritis*" or "ankylosing spondyloarthritis*" or "axial spondyloarthritis*" or "spondylarthritis ankylopoietica" or "spondyloarthritis ankylopoietica" or "rheumatoid spondylitis" or "spondylitis rheumatoid").ti,ab,kf.

32. exp Urinary Tract Infections/ or exp Cystitis/ or exp Vaginitis/ or exp Prostatitis/ or ((genito-urinary adj3 infection*) or (genitourinary adj3 infection*) or ("urogenital tract*" adj3 infection*) or (inflammat* adj3 urogenital*) or ("tractus urogenitalis" adj3 infection*) or (urogenital* adj3 infection*) or ("urinary tract" adj3

infection*) or cystiti* or (bladder adj3 inflammat*) or megacystitis* or pericystitis* or vaginiti* or (vagina* adj3 inflammat*) or colpitis or kolpitis or prostatitis* or (prostate adj3 infection*).ti,ab,kf.

33. exp Disease Outbreaks/ or exp Endemic Diseases/ or (epidemic* or outbreak* or endemic*).ti,ab,kf.

34. or/16-33

35. "epidemiology".fs. or exp Epidemiologic Methods/ or exp Epidemiologic Studies/ or exp Sentinel Surveillance/ or exp Seroepidemiologic Studies/ or exp Cohort Studies/ or exp Cross-sectional Studies/ or exp Longitudinal Studies/ or exp Follow-up Studies/ or exp Prospective Studies/ or exp Cross-Over Studies/

36. (prevalence or incidence or epidemiol* or survey or rapid assessment or situation assessment or situational assessment or rar or cohort or surveillance or seroprevalence or seroincidence or seroepidemiol* or screening or frequency or occurrence).mp.

37. (((ecological or "follow up" or observational or prospective or cross-over or crossover) adj (studies or study)) or (longitudinal or retrospective or cross-sectional or transversal) or (association adj2 (studies or study))).ti,ab,kf. or (association or associations).ti.

38. or/35-37

39. 9 and 34 and 38

40. 15 or 39

41. exp Animals/ not Humans/

42. (news or editorial or letter).pt.

43. 40 not (41 or 42)

44. remove duplicates from 43

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599 4.6.3 Data items & sample codebook

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601 Our data items & sample codebook can be accessed through OSF: <https://osf.io/4v52e/>

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604 4.6.4. Table 4. Examples of Health Outcomes

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Health Outcome Area	Examples
Respiratory tract	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • pneumonia • asthma • chronic obstructive pulmonary disease • pulmonary function
Eyes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • conjunctivitis • watery eyes • ocular discharge
Skin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • atopic dermatitis • rash • erythema

Gastrointestinal tract	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • diarrhea • enteritis • inflammatory bowel disease
Cardiovascular system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • hypertension • angina • myocardial infarction
Genitourinary tract	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • genitourinary tract infection • urinary tract infection • cystitis • vaginitis • prostatitis
Infectious Disease	<p>Carriage/colonization of or infection with any of the following pathogens:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> • <i>Coxiella burnetti</i> • <i>Clostridioides difficile</i>
Immune-mediated disease	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • rheumatoid arthritis • psoriasis • uveitis • hypothyroidism • hyperthyroidism • systemic lupus erythematosus • multiple sclerosis • ankylosing spondylitis
Cancer	
Mental health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • anxiety • depression • vertigo
Birth outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fetal growth retardation • stillbirth • preterm birth
Healthcare utilization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • medication use • clinic visits • hospitalization
Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • quality of life • absenteeism from work or school

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• mortality
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